

Assessment of Awareness and Perception of Green Building by Occupants in Selected Certified Office Buildings in Lagos Nigeria

Abstract.

Globally, human needs for survival have exerted enormous pressure on the environment due to urbanization. Office buildings consume excessive amounts of energy and other resources, thereby releasing greenhouse gases into the environment. Green building (GB) has been used globally as a tool to reduce these negative environmental impacts, which in turn increase the building's performance and value. The benefits of GB have helped most developed cities mitigate environmental issues. Despite the various GB benefits from which the occupants and owners can derive, the level of awareness of GB implementation in Nigeria is extremely low, with no reliable assessment tools. Therefore, the study assessed occupants' awareness and perception of GB in selected certified office buildings. 73 of 100 structured questionnaires were used to collect data and returned for analysis using frequency counts and the relative perceptive index. The study revealed that 78.1% of the occupants were not aware of the GB office being certified, while 21.9% were aware of the GB office being certified. A mean score of 2.89 (RPI = 0.5078) on cost-efficient, 1.93 (RPI = 0.386) on ease of maintenance, and 1.86 (RPI = 0.372) on landscaping were perceived based on economic and environmental views, which implies that the occupants viewed GB as being high in cost and maintenance. The study recommends more public awareness of the benefits of GB, and its rating system, government intervention on enabling policies and bureaucracy in building approval processes, and empowerment of the existing GB certification council in Lagos.

Keywords: Green Building Certification, Awareness, Occupants' Perception, High-Rise Office Building, Lagos

1. Introduction

The adverse impact of urbanization globally has compelled developed cities to prioritize sustainable building development. (Dahiru et al., 2014). According to Daramola et al. (2012), in designing for sustainable construction or development, the adoption of sustainable materials with alternative and renewable energy will aid the more widespread implementation of green architecture and sustainable development. Buildings at a global level use about 40% of energy, 25% of water, and 40% of resources and emit about 33% of greenhouse gases. (United Nations, 2017) Conventional buildings, such as office buildings, consume excessive amounts of energy and other resources, thereby releasing greenhouse gases into the environment. Almost two and a half times energy are used per square meter of floor space needed in high-rise office buildings with twenty stories or more than in low-rise office buildings with six stories or less. (Philip, 2015) Taking the styles and prominent vertical facade into consideration, to achieve effective occupant livability, the design must achieve efficient

consideration for facilities, service, and management (Alagbe & Aina 2020). The amount of energy used in high-rise buildings has gone from 38% to 61% of the total amount of energy used in commercial buildings. (Opoko & Oluwatayo, 2014) Nigeria's per capita energy consumption is 120.5 kWh, which is more than ten times below the global average. Nigerian cities are growing rapidly due to urbanization but lack revolutionary tools to improve the construction industry (Ogunmakinde & Umeh, 2018; Dalharthat, 2020; Akadiri & Omishakin, 2020). According to Daramola & Eziyi (2010), cultural factors are identified as the major urban environmental challenges, apart from the climatic and political factors of the government.

Furthermore, the study emphasized the importance of the psychological orientation of people in playing a key role in addressing urban environmental challenges. Some of the environmental challenges that are orchestrated by buildings, as identified by the WGBC, are urban explosion, water pollution, air pollution, poor solid waste management, deforestation, and the depletion of ozone layers from the burning of fossil fuels that result in high earth temperatures and energy consumption. To mitigate these challenges, green building has been identified as a revolutionary tool. Green building (GB) is used as a tool to reduce these negative environmental impacts by increasing the overall performance and value of buildings. The green building concept, which has environmental, economic, and social wellbeing benefits, has helped most developed cities mitigate environmental issues. Dahiru et al. (2014) established that green building has not been practiced in Nigeria due to a lack of government legislative policies for stakeholders, even though they are aware of GB practices and the variety of benefits. The general public's awareness of GB and buildings being certified is also low. On the contrary, Adeogun (2022) argues that there is a practice of GB development in Nigeria, specifically in Lagos, although at a developing stage due to the unavailability of enabling government policies, low professional participation, and adoption in practice despite the economic, social, and environmental benefits of GB. Therefore, it is important to note that Nigeria needs to do more to catch up with the rest of the world in embracing GB.

In addition, despite the various GB assessment tools available and the wide range of benefits of green building certification (GBC) that can be derived by both occupants and owners, the level of awareness of green building implementation in Nigeria is very low and there are no sustainable building assessment tools. As reported by Reeds et al. (2009), GB rating or certification systems, which date back to 1990s, rate or reward for achieving a specific environmental performance or level of compliance by creating environmentally friendly and resource-efficient building life cycles from siting to design, construction, operation, maintenance, renovation, and demolition. (Stephanie, 2019) However, different parts of the world have embraced the adoption of these notable certification systems, such as Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) in the USA; Building Research Establishment's Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) in the UK; Green Star in South Africa; and the Estidama or Pearl rating system in Dubai, which have almost the same climate as Nigeria. Nigeria does not have a specific effective rating system except for the Excellence in Design for Greater Efficiencies (EDGE) certifications in conjunction with the World Green Building Certifications (WGBC) in Lagos. The rating systems vary from one country to another due to the climatic conditions, cultural pedigree, and occupants' psychological orientations, using different criteria and ratings. Currently, more than one hundred building certification systems exist around the world. (Birgisdottir, 2018; Reed et al., 2009).

Opoko (2014) earlier stated that Nigeria's per capita energy consumption is 120.5 kWh, which is more than ten times below the global average. Brazil and Pakistan, which have about the same number of people as Nigeria, produce twenty-four times and five times more electricity

than Nigeria, respectively. Bangladesh, which has a smaller population and a lower gross domestic product (GDP), produces twice as much electricity as Nigeria. The study focused on the awareness and perceptions of occupants of GB in certified offices in Lagos, Nigeria. Lagos is a megacity with about 15.38 million people in 2022. (United Nations Population Prospects, 2021) It is also known as the most economically viable state (Nigeria Congress, 2005), with a total output of 136 billion dollars, which is more than a third of Nigeria's GDP (Financial Times, 2017), and would have been the fifth-largest economy in Africa if it were a country (Ekundayo, 2013). It has a higher concentration of high-rise office buildings in Nigeria, accounting for approximately 60% of the country's commercial construction projects, including high-rise office buildings and residential development (Adebakin, 2016). Thus, the study is important because of the gaps identified in the literature on sustainable buildings, such as GB legislation, stakeholders' unawareness, low implementation, lack of awareness from owners and developers, government policies, the high cost of sustainable materials and products, and the expertise of experts on assessment schemes for rating buildings. Given the need to increase the number of implementations of GB in Nigeria, it is important to investigate the occupants' or owners' awareness and perception of GB as a tool to mitigate environmental issues and improve property value and wellbeing. Hence, the study aims to assess the occupants' perceptions of GB in selected certified office buildings in Lagos to influence green building implementation. The research objectives are to determine the levels and medium of awareness of GB in certified offices and examine occupants' perceptions of GB in certified offices in Lagos.

2. Literature review

2.1 Green Building and Green Building Certifications Systems

Green building adoption tends to sustain the environment and preserve available natural resources, considering a minimalistic approach to reducing environmental degradation caused by building practices. Different definitions and benefits of green building and rating systems are shortlisted, as shown in Table 1 below. According to WGBC (2022), green building rating tools (also known as certification systems) are used to assess and recognize buildings that meet certain green requirements or standards. GBCS is often voluntary, recognizing and rewarding companies and organizations that build and operate greener buildings, thereby encouraging and incentivizing them to push the boundaries of sustainability. Globally, developed cities and countries have embraced the concept of GB. (Samer, 2013) The study by Shaba and Noir (2014) shows that the Green Building Council has been inaugurated in Nigeria, although with poor membership and the unavailability of reliable building assessment tools. Furthermore, Reed, Bilos, Wilkinson, and Schulte (2009) reported that the GB practice of using rating tools for assessment dates to 1990, with the Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method (BREEAM) being the first recommended rating tool in the United Kingdom. BREEAM evaluates water and energy consumption, pollution, health and wellbeing, material and waste management, transport, ecology, and management through scientific-based tools by independent licensed assessors, adopting the grades of "good" (45), "very good" (55), "excellent" (70), and "outstanding" (85). The Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED) program was established in 1996 in the USA and focused on low carbon emissions, improved efficiency, cost-saving GB, and boosting the wellbeing of the people by adopting these ratings: certified (40-49 points), silver (50-59 points), gold (60-69 points), and platinum (80+ points). In addition, Green Star has been adopted in South Africa, which uses the same rating tool as LEED. Furthermore, to increase the number of certified green buildings in Nigeria, Adegbile's (2013) study proposed LEED as a green building rating system for the Nigerian construction industry. However, Adeogun (2022) recommends the Pearls or Estidama

rating systems used in Arab emirates for Nigeria due to the similar climatic conditions by focusing on sustainable design, construction, and operation of communities, buildings, and villas, which is like LEED with three certification levels administered by Pearls Qualified Professionals (PQPs). In addition, to select rating tools for buildings, various factors must be considered, such as the country’s climatic conditions, availability of materials, land, cultural adaptation, population growth, public awareness, and legal support. Furthermore, adaptable rating tools such as building configuration, landscaping, building materials, the building envelope, and water and energy efficiency must be considered. (Tamaraukuro, 2016) These are classified under the GB features or goals, such as life cycle assessment, efficiency in structure, and site design. Operations and maintenance, optimization efficient use of energy, water, use of renewable energy (solar energy); pollution and waste reduction and recycling and good indoor environmental air quality. use of materials that are non-toxic, ethical, and sustainable waste reduction, environmental consideration in designs, construction, and operation; consideration of the quality of life of occupants in design, construction, and operation; and a design that enables adaptation to a changing environment (WGBC, 2022).

Table 1: Definitions of GB

Green Building Definitions	Sources
A process of creating buildings and infrastructure in a way that minimizes the use of resources, reduces harmful effects on ecology, and creates a better environment for occupants	<i>Chatterjee (2009)</i>
Reduce the environmental footprint of buildings in comparison with standard practices.	<i>Fischer (2010)</i>
Focuses on increasing the sufficiency of resource use (energy, water, and materials) while reducing building impacts on human health and the environment during the building’s lifecycle through better location, design, construction, operation, maintenance, and removal.	<i>Kamana & Escultura (2011)</i>
An outcome of a design philosophy that focuses on increasing the efficiency of resource use	<i>Pan, Dzeng, & Yang (2011)</i>
Healthy facilities had been designed and built in a resource-efficient manner, using ecologically based principles.	<i>Ahn, Pearce, & Wang (2013)</i>
a practice in which buildings are designed and built to have a prominent level of environmental, economic, and social performance throughout their lifecycle without causing environmental degradation. The potential for improving the environment by harnessing the expertise and practices in the built environment makes green building a viable option.	<i>David, O. N., and Olabode E. O. (2015).</i>
Also known as "green construction" or "sustainable building," this term refers to both a structure and the application of processes that are environmentally responsible and resource-efficient throughout a building's life cycle: from planning to design, construction, operation, maintenance, renovation, and demolition. This requires the close cooperation of the contractor, the architects, the engineers, and the client at all project stages. Green building practice expands and complements the classical building design concerns of economy, utility, durability, and comfort. In doing so, the three dimensions of sustainability—planet, people, and profit—across the entire supply chain need to be considered.	<i>Yan & Stellios (2006), US-EPA (2008), US-EPA (2009), Solaimani & Sedighi (2019)</i>

2.1.1 Benefits of Green Building and Green Building Certification Systems

Table 2: Benefits of GB and GB Certifications

Environmental	Economical	Health & Social
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Less water usage 2. Lower energy consumption 3. Increased biodiversity 4. Reduced emission of greenhouse 6. Catching up with the rest of the World 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cost savings on utilities. 2. Lower construction cost 3. Increased property values and occupancy rates 4. Job Creation 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase human social performance 2. Improved health and well-being of people.

Source: WGBC (2022)

2.2 Awareness of Occupants of GB

Brown and Cole's (2008) study assessed occupants' knowledge and perception of GB based on the energy efficiency of office buildings using a website-based survey. The result shows that the occupants of the six office buildings have low knowledge of GB, although they affirm that they are comfortable in the office building environment. However, AlSanad et al. (2011)'s research on stakeholders' level of awareness, perception, and acceptability of green building in the Kuwaiti construction industry shows a moderate level of awareness and knowledge of GB adoption and implementation. According to Jamison's (2008) study on occupants' awareness and perception of GB in Washington State, the result shows that all of the respondents are unaware of the meaning of "green" and its benefits, although they are familiar with the features of "green" buildings in comparison. Samarasinghe (2012) examined the awareness and perceptions of occupants in Sri Lankan green houses. The result shows that it was discovered that implementation of GB is dependent not only on awareness of GB features but also on the economic, social, and health of the people. Furthermore, sustainability awareness encompasses the purpose of sustainable design (environmental protection, natural resource protection, life cycle cost reduction, economic value preservation, comfort, and health in the building, and social value preservation), the fundamental concept, and the relationship of the project life cycle to sustainable design rating. Chokor et al. (2015) and Kim et al. (2017) To ensure the rapid development of green buildings, a green building certification system that provides basic guarantees for financial support and tax subsidies is recommended. (Wang et al., 2021)

Bungwon et al. (2016) investigated property users and stakeholders in the United Kingdom. The result shows that the awareness level of green building is low in Kaduna because of a variety of hindrances to its adoption, such as a lack of technological innovations, a lack of skilled experts, poor sensitization of professional organizations on sustainable design and implementation, and a lack of investor or client interest in green building. In addition, different studies affirm that Nigerian professionals in the building industry are familiar with the concept of green building and its benefits and are aware of green building in practice. Ameh et al. (2007); Waniko (2014); Nduka and Ogunsanmi (2015); and Bungwon et al. (2016). Furthermore, Markson and Matthew's (2018) study in Nigeria assessed occupants' awareness based on the level of awareness of the users and the medium through which the users were aware of green buildings. The level of awareness being evaluated using green building features and measured with a Likert scale. The results show that all the occupants are unaware of GBs and their features. Furthermore, the medium of awareness of the users of GB was evaluated based on television, websites, friends and family, and newspapers and magazines. This result shows that many of the occupants who were aware of the buildings got to know about them through television.

According to Abimbola (2015), some challenges that discouraged GB implementation included GB legislation, unawareness of stakeholders, and low implementation. Clients' owners' or developers' lack of awareness, government policies, the high cost of sustainable materials and products, and experts on assessment schemes for rating buildings (David & Olabode, 2015) Adegbile (2013) opined that there is a need to incorporate GB ratings to aid implementation, while Abolore (2012) and Otegbulu (2011) studies emphasized professionals' and occupants' perceptions of sustainable development.

2.3 Perception of Occupants of GB

The WBCSD (2007) study revealed that the level of awareness of GB among occupants, corporate owners, and professionals in the eight selected countries is extremely high despite their low participation in GB implementations, based on phone and physical interviews across the countries. Unfortunately, the study failed to involve private property owners. However, Khalfan et al.'s (2015) study shows that the owner and employees' perceptions hinder the adoption of GBs in practice. The results include eco-friendly materials; financial incentives to owners and occupants; awareness of GB by professionals, owners, and users; and enabling the government to be the driver for green building implementations. Furthermore, Mohammed's (2019) study in Indonesia highlighted 25 criteria to measure occupants' perception of GBs, such as appropriate site development, site selection, stormwater management, site landscaping, energy efficiency & conservation, building envelope, ventilation, natural lighting, low energy elements, environmentally friendly refrigerants, renewable energy, vertical transportation, water conservation and recycling, environmentally friendly materials, building, and material reuse, indoor air health & comfort, CO₂ monitoring, thermal comfort, acoustic level management, building environment management, waste management, and accredited expert monitoring.

In comparison, Markson & Matthew's (2018) study examines the users' perceptions based on their reactions to GB features. As a result, GB parameters such as lower environmental hazards, the preservation of natural resources, the availability of parks, greenbelts, hiking trails, and landscaping, healthy indoor air, higher GB construction costs, the use of recycled materials in green buildings, and more convenient living conditions are being adopted by the people. The water efficiency of green buildings "has a mean value," as do energy efficiency, use of high-quality materials, durability of green buildings, ease of maintenance, lower utility costs, and cost efficiency. The result shows that users' perceptions are more skewed towards the environmental standpoint relative to social and economic standpoints, and users perceive green buildings to be less cost-effective than conventional buildings. This shows that less awareness of the GB features by the users validates the low implementation of GB in Nigeria, as professionals in the built environment depend on the occupants' or owners' perception. Furthermore, Nduka and Ogunsanmi's (2015) study focused on Nigeria's construction industry's awareness and perception of green building. The result shows that most professionals are aware of GB and its benefits, thereby recommending the inauguration of a green building assessment body that drives the prompt certification of both new and retrofitted buildings and helps to create more awareness for the public. Throughout the review of literature, there is not sufficient literature that addresses occupants' awareness and perception of green buildings, as most literature focuses more on professionals' evaluation of the post-occupancy of green buildings and more on the adoption of GBs. Due to this, this research breaches the gap for further future studies as it assesses the occupant's awareness and perception of GB.

2.3 High-rise office buildings in Lagos

According to Anthony (2014), high-rise buildings in Nigeria are being built due to overpopulation because of urbanization, insufficient land mass, and overpriced land values—factors that compel property owners to build such building typologies. Furthermore, it is marked by numerous challenges, such as fire, terrorist attack, and building collapse. Lagos is a megacity with about 15.38 million people in 2022. (United Nations Population Prospects, 2021) It is also known as the most economically viable state (Nigeria Congress, 2005), with a

total output of 136 billion dollars, which is more than a third of Nigeria's GDP (Financial Times, 2017), and would have been the fifth-largest economy in Africa if it were a country (Ekundayo, 2013). It has a greater concentration of high-rise office buildings than any other state in Nigeria, with about 60% of the country's commercial construction projects such as high-rise office buildings and residential development (Adebakin, 2016).

3. Methodology

This study investigates the occupants' perceptions of GB in selected certified high-rise office buildings with a view to influencing GB implementation in Nigeria. The research design randomly sampled the occupants of five selected certified office buildings within Lagos out of the seven certified office buildings reported by EDGE Certifications Nigeria in 2021, and based on research ethics, the names of these buildings and occupants were protected. Lagos was studied based on its being the largest city in sub-Saharan Africa and the economic hub of Nigeria, with the highest number of office buildings and over 60% of the country's construction projects (Nigeria Congress, 2005; Ekundayo, 2013; Adebakin, 2016). Secondary data was collected through a review of relevant literature, which assisted in the design of the structured questionnaire on levels and mediums of awareness of GB in the selected certified offices and examined occupants' perceptions of GB in the selected certified office buildings in the study area. In addition, these buildings were selected because they have the criteria or features of LEED, which was recommended as a rating tool for Nigeria in Adegbile's (2013) study, in which its parameters were coined for easy understanding by the respondents. All these are important to ensure adequate and accurate views of the respondents when investigating their level of awareness and perception of GB in certified offices in Lagos. A total of 100 well-structured questionnaires were distributed to all five randomly selected certified high-rise office buildings in Lagos due to limited access to the population of respondents. 73 of the questionnaires were returned and used for analysis. This accounts for a 73% response rate and is believed adequate for the study. The first section was designed to collect brief respondents' relevant information and assess occupants' level and medium of awareness of GB in the selected certified offices by adopting a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 being not aware at all, 2 being slightly aware, 3 being somewhat aware, 4 being moderately aware, and 5 being extremely aware. The second section gathered relevant information on occupants' perceptions of GB in certified offices by adopting a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 being very satisfied, 2 being satisfied, 3 being unsure, 4 being dissatisfied, and 5 being very dissatisfied. The result was analyzed using frequency counts and measures of the relative perceptive index, adopting the IBM SPSS Statistics 26 tool.

4. Result and Discussions

The result of this research is being discussed based on the objectives of the study, as shown in Tables 3 and 4. The first section discusses the respondents' characteristics, level, and medium of awareness of the occupants of GB in certified office buildings. The last section discusses occupants' perceptions of green buildings in the selected certified offices based on green building features and LEED rating system.

4.1 Occupants' Awareness of GB in Certified Office Buildings

Table 3 discusses results on the respondents' characteristics, level, and medium of awareness of GB in selected certified office buildings. The results show 89% of respondents were staff,

while 11% were employers or facility managers, and they were all educated. 57 (78.1%) of the occupants were very much unaware of GB being certified, while 10 (13.7%) were slightly aware, and 6 (8.2%) were unaware of GB being certified. This result shows that the majority of the occupants of the buildings were not aware of GB being certified or of GB's features as a green product. Furthermore, Table 3 shows that 11 (15.1%) of the occupants were aware of GB being certified through their friends and family; 7 (9.6%) of the occupants were aware of GB being certified through newspapers and magazines; 32 (43.8%) of the occupants were aware of GB being certified through television; and 23 (31.5%) of the occupants were aware of GB being certified through websites. This result shows that most of the occupants were aware of GB being certified through their television and websites. The result shows the significant impact of media on occupants' awareness of GB being certified.

Table 3: Occupants' level of awareness of green buildings being certified.

	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
A	Level of Education		
	Secondary	8	11.0
	Tertiary	65	89.0
	Total	73	100
B	Job Title		
	Employer	6	8.2
	Staff	65	89.0
	Facility Manager	2	2.7
	Total	73	100
C	Level of Awareness		
	Not aware at all	57	78.1
	Slightly aware	10	13.7
	Moderate aware	6	8.2
	Total	73	100
D	Medium of Awareness		
	Friend/Family	11	15.1
	Newspaper/Magazines	7	9.6
	Televisions	32	43.8
	Website	23	31.5
	Total	73	100

4.2 Occupants' Perception of GB In Certified Office Buildings Based on LEED

The table 4 below assessed the occupants' perception of GB being certified. The following LEED criteria were used to assess the occupants' perceptions of GB in selected certified office buildings such as integrative thinking, energy, water, waste, materials, location & transportation, sustainable sites, health & human experience, regional impacts, innovation, and global, regional, local context. The results show the three highest mean scores of cost efficiency at 2.89 with Relative Perceptive Index of (RPI) of 0.5078, ease of maintenance has a mean score of 1.93 with RPI of 0.386, and landscaping has mean score of 1.86 with 0.372 RPI. These three features have the highest mean score in ascending order which tends towards the economic and environmental point of view of the occupants. The means score falls within 2 and very close to 3. This implies that they are satisfied with GB with the uncertainty GB being affordable to build. Furthermore, the table 4 below shows that the three less perceived features of GB in the selected certified office buildings in descending ranks which are automatic features with mean score of 1.42 and 0.284 RPI, mean score of 1.37 on ease of access to public transport with 0.274 RPI and mean score of 1.33 with 0.266 RPI for built with quality material.

However, the as seen from the table, majority of the means score on the LEED parameters falls within the rank of 1 and 2 which implies that the occupant are satisfied with the features of green building implementations.

Table 4: Occupants’ perception of GB in certified office buildings based on LEED

1-very satisfied; 2-satisfied; 3-unsure; 4- dissatisfied; 5-very dissatisfied									
Frequencies									
LEED GB Certification Parameters	1	2	3	4	5	Sum	Mean	RPI	Variables Ranking
Cost efficient	5	30	7	30	1	73	2.89	0.5078	1
Ease of maintenance	13	55	2	3	0	73	1.93	0.386	2
Landscaping	15	54	3	1	0	73	1.86	0.372	3
Built with re-usable materials	26	36	7	4	0	73	1.85	0.37	4
Convenient indoor living condition	15	57	1	0	0	73	1.81	0.362	5
Reduce water usage	16	57	0	0	0	73	1.78	0.356	6
Reduce energy usage	17	56	0	0	0	73	1.77	0.354	7
Lower environment effect	25	46	2	0	0	73	1.68	0.336	8
Preserve natural resources	33	38	1	1	0	73	1.59	0.318	9
Automatic features	43	29	1	0	0	73	1.42	0.284	10
Ease of access to public transport	48	24	0	1	0	73	1.37	0.274	11
Built with quality material	50	22	1	0	0	73	1.33	0.266	12

5.0 Conclusion

The result revealed that, despite the educational qualifications of the respondents, the level of awareness of green building benefits and green buildings on being certified was extremely low. Green building awareness was spread primarily through television and websites, but also through newspapers and magazines. Respondents' perceptions of green building features and green buildings being certified tend toward economic and environmental benefits. The economic benefit, with the highest mean score of 2.8, further shows the misconception that green building is not affordable. The study recommends more awareness among the key players in the construction industry by using available media. In addition, new policies should be enacted to curb the bureaucratic approach to the building approval process, and the government should enact policies that encourage investors to invest more in real estate development, as these will help to increase the number of green buildings and green building certifications in Lagos and every other part of the country. An incentive in the form of motivation can be provided to stakeholders in the construction industry. The existing green building certification body (EDGE) in Lagos should be empowered to allow for more affordable certification.

References

- Abimbola, O. W. (2015). Understanding the gap between green building practice and legislative requirements in South Africa. emeraldgroupublishing.com/licensing/reprints.htm
- Adebakin, I.H., and Ipaye, T.O. (2016). Project Delivery Delay: The Nigeria Experience IOSR Journal of Mechanical and Civil Engineering (IOSR-JMCE) e-ISSN: 2278-1684, p-ISSN: 2320-334X, Volume 13, Issue 5 Ver. V (Sep. - Oct. 2016), PP 84-87 www.iosrjournals.org

- Adedeji Daramola, and Eziyi, O.I. (2010). Urban Environmental Problems in Nigeria: Implications for Sustainable Development. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa* (Volume 12, No.1, 2010) ISSN: 1520-5509 Clarion University of Pennsylvania, Clarion, Pennsylvania
- Adegbile, M.B. (2013). Assessment and Adaptation of an Appropriate Green Building Rating System for Nigeria. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*, 3, 2224-3216. United Nations Report, <https://news.un.org/en/story/2017/06/560022-world-population-hit-98-billion-2050-despite-nearly-universal-lower-fertility#>. WU1IaVPytZ0 (2017)
- Adeogun, M.G. (2022). Assessment of Architects' Adoption of Green Smart Design Strategies in High-Rise Office Buildings in Lagos Nigeria. *Proceedings of the 12th CIDB Research Conference*. Johannesburg, South Africa. Springer Publication.
- Adebakin, I.H., and Ipaye, T.O.: Project Delivery Delay: The Nigeria Experience *IOASR, IOASR-JMCE*, 13(5),84-87
- Ahn, Y.H., Pearce, A.R., Wang, Y., and Wang, G. (2013). Drivers and Barriers of Sustainable Design and Construction: The perception of Green Building Experience. *International Journal of Sustainable Building Technology*, 4 (1): 35-45.
- Akadiri, P.O., and Omishakin, A.J. (2020). Trends in BIM research application in Nigeria AEC Industry. *IRJET* 07(07),1345-1351.
- Alagbe, O.A., Aina, B. (2020). Assessment Of Residential Satisfaction of a Typical High Rise Residential Building in Lagos, Nigeria. *Psychology And Education* (2020) 57(9): 2711-2720. ISSN: 00333077
- AlSanad, S., Gale, G., and Edward, R. (2011). Challenges of Sustainable Construction in Kuwait: Investigating the level of Awareness of Kuwait Stakeholders. *Word Academy of Science, Engineering, and Technology*, 59 (1): 2197-2204.
- Ameh, O. J., Isijiola, S.J., and Achi, F.O. (2007). Assessment of the Sustainability of Public Buildings in Lagos, Nigeria. *Construction Research Journal*, 1(1): 46- 54.
- Anthony, N.E. (2014). Challenges Affecting the Development and Optimal Use of Tall Buildings in Nigeria. *The International Journal of Engineering and Science*. Vol.3, Issue, 4.
- Birgisdottir, J.H., and Kasper, G. (2018). *Guide to sustainable building certifications*. ISBN97887-563-18815
- Brown, Z.B., and Cole, R.J. (2008). *Engaging Occupants in Green Building Performance: Addressing the Knowledge Gap*. ACEEE Summer Study on Energy Efficiency in Buildings.
- Bungwon, H.D., Dabo, D.I. and Ishaya, D.A. (2016). A Study of the Awareness of Property Managers and Other Built Environment Professionals on Sustainable Buildings in Kaduna Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Chemical, Metallurgical and Civil Engg. (IJRCMCE)* Vol. 3, Pp. 94-96. ISSN 2349-1442 EISSN 2349-1450
- Chokor, A., El Asmar, M., Tilton, C., and Srour, I., 2015). A dual assessment framework to evaluate LEED-certified facilities' occupant satisfaction and energy performance: macro and micro approaches. *J. Archit. Eng.* 22 (4), A4015003. Dahiru, A., Dania, A., Adejoh, A. (2014). An Investigation into the Prospects of Green Building Practice in Nigeria. Vol. 7, No. 6; Canadian Center of Science and Education
- Dalhartlhat, N. (2020). Level of BIM awareness and application in the Nigeria AEC Industry, Minna, Nigeria: The Federal University of Technology, Minna

- David, O. N., and Olabode E. O. (2015). Stakeholders Perception of Factors Determining the Adoptability of Green Building Practices in Construction Projects in Nigeria. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science* www.iiste.org ISSN 2224-3216 (Paper) ISSN 2225-0948 (Online) Vol.5, No.2, 2015
- Ekundayo, J.M. (2016). *Out of Africa: Fashola reinventing servant leadership to engender Nigeria's transformation*. Lagos state P135.ISBN9781790406 (2013) twenty-four.
- Financial Times (2017). Nigeria's Economy is why Lagos works. Nigeria: Financial times. <http://www.ft.com/content/ff0595e4-26de-11e8-b27e-cc62a39d57a0>
- Fischer, E.A. (2010). *Issues in Green Building and the Federal Response: An Introduction*. Congressional Research Service. Retrieved August 13, 2013, from <http://www.crs.gov>
- Green Building-US EPA. (2008). (<http://www.epa.gov/greenbuilding/pubs/about.htm>).
- Khalfan, M.M., Noor, A., Maqsood, T., Alshabri, N., and Sagoo, A. (2015). Perceptions towards Sustainable Construction amongst Construction Contractors in State of Victoria, Australia. *Journal of Economics, Business, and Management*, Vol. 3, No. 10. Pp. 940-947
- Kamana, C.P., and Escultura (2011). Building Green to Attain Sustainability. *International Journal of Earth Sciences and Engineering*, 4(4): 725-729
- Kim, J., Hyun, J.Y., Chong, W.K.O., and Ariaratnam, S. (2017). Understanding the effects of environmental factors on building energy efficiency designs and credits case studies using data mining and real-time data. *J. Eng. Des. Technol.* 15 (3).
- Mohammed, A. B., Perdana, M., Retno, W., and Abdur Rohim, B.B. (2019). Stakeholders' perspectives on green building rating: A case study in Indonesia. *Heliyon* 5 (2019)
- Markson, K., and Matthew, O.O. (2018). Awareness and Perception of Office Property Users on green building in Lagos Nigeria. *Journal of Built Environment and Sustainability*.
- Nduka, D.O., and Ogunsanmi, O.E. (2015) Construction Professionals' Perception on Green Building Awareness and Accruable Benefits in Construction Projects in Nigeria. *Covenant Journal of Research in the Built Environment (CJRBE)* Vol.3, No.2. p30-52
- Nigeria Congress. (2005). Administrative division description Lagos Nigeria.
- Ogunmakinde, E.O., and Umeh, S. (2018). *Adoption of BIM in the Nigeria AEC Industry*. AUBEA: Curtin University, Singapore
- Oluwole, A., and Aina, B. (2020). Assessment of Residential Satisfaction of a Typical High Rise Residential Building in Lagos, Nigeria. *Psychology And Education*. 57(9): 2711-2720 ISSN: 00333077
- Opoko, A., and Oluwatayo, A. (2014). Trends in Urbanization: Implication for Planning and Low-Income Housing Delivery in Lagos, Nigeria. *Architecture Research*, pp.15-26
- Otegbulu, A. (2011). Economics of Green Design and Environmental Sustainability. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 4, 240-248.
- Pan, N.F., Dzung, R.J., & Yang, M.D. (2011). Decision Making Behaviors in Planning Green Building. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Computer Distributed Control and Intelligent Environmental Monitoring*, 1710-1713, 19- 20 February, Changsha Hunan, China
- Philip, S. (2017). High-rise buildings are much more energy-intensive than low-rise. Publication of University College London (2017, June 29) retrieved 31 January 2023 from

- Daramola, S.A., Toyin, A., and Damilola, A. (2012). Green Architecture and Sustainable Development in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Development and Environmental Protection* Vol.2 No.2
- Samarasinghe, D.S. (2012) Green Home Concept: Consumer's Perception towards Green Homes in Sri Lanka. *Indian journal of research*. Volume: one, Issue 10. Pp. 138 – 140
- Solaimani, S., and Sedighi, M. (2019). Toward a holistic view on Lean sustainable construction: a literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.
- Tamaraukuro, T.A., Jubril, A., and George, B. (2016). Development of a building performance assessment and design tool for residential buildings in Nigeria *International High-Performance Built Environment Conference – A Sustainable Built Environment Conference 2016 Series (SBE16)*
- UN-World Population Prospect (2021). <https://www.stat.si/StatWeb/en/News/Index/9566>
- U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. (2009). Green Building Basic Information. <http://www.epa.gov/greenbuilding/pubs/about.htm>
- Reed, Richard & Bilos, Anita & Wilkinson, Sara & Schulte, Karl-Werner. (2009). International comparison of sustainable rating tools. *Journal of Sustainable Real Estate*.
- Wang, W., Tian, Z., Xi, W., Tan, Y.R., and Deng, Y. (2021). The influencing factors of China's green building development: an analysis using RBF-WINGS method, *Build. Environ.* 188 107425, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2020.107425>.
- Waniko, D.P. (2014). Green Building in Nigeria: Emerging Opportunities for Quantity Surveying Profession. Retrieved from <http://www.alive2green.com/greenbuilding>.
- WBCSD (2009). Energy efficiency in buildings: Transforming the market, World Business Council for Sustainable Development, Geneva.
- World Green Building Council-WGBC (2022). About Green Building. <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>
- Yan, J., and Stellios, P. (2006). Design for Sustainability. Beijing: China Architecture and Building Press. ISBN 7-112-08390-7